

Management Accounting Systems: Determining Factors And Its Impact On Company Performance

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Abstract

This explanatory research examines the influence of corporate risk management, knowledge management, and CEO spirituality on company performance, with the management accounting system as a mediating variable. Data were collected using questionnaires with a sample of 166 hospital directors in East Java Province in Indonesia, then analyzed by Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), with WarpPLS. The results showed that corporate risk and knowledge management positively influenced the accounting system and company performance. Furthermore, CEO spirituality influenced the accounting system but did not affect company performance. The management accounting system mediates the influence of corporate risk and knowledge management on company performance in a complementary manner. However, the management accounting system does not mediate the influence of CEO spirituality on company performance.

Introduction

A management accounting system refers to the systematic use of management accounting to attain organizational goals (Busco dan Scapens, 2011; Mia dan Chenhall, 1994; Rasid dkk., 2014). It is an integral part of the management process because it covers the provision and use of financial information. Generally, management accounting is operational for managers in organizations for decision making, planning, and control. A well-designed and proper management accounting system helps managers be more effective in decision making, improve their organizations' efficiency and stay competitive against dynamic business environments (Rasid dkk., 2014; Reid dan Smith, 2000). The company's response ability to changes in the business environment provides an advantage to maintain or increase its market share and performance.

According to the contingency theory, company managers should control all their resources for effective performance. A management accounting system is a tool prepared by to help control all their potential resources. Risk management is one of the efforts to control all potential perils. It is a management effort to collect and organize all information related to the possible risks.

The management uses the information to counter the risks resulting from environmental changes. Therefore, a management accounting system should be designed to organize data on each business line and its competitors. Company managers use these data as a business decision (Reid dan Smith, 2000). The management accounting system assists company managers in making quick decisions based on their potential. The convenience provided by the management accounting system encourages company managers to establish the correct data concerning their potential for the right decision-making.

Resources must be appropriately managed with all the potential knowledge possessed by the company. Therefore, knowledge management directs the company to accumulate and synergize each departmental information to be further managed. A competent management accounting system must accompany these efforts. The management accounting system chooses the company knowledge that is suitable for improving business processes (Mia dan Chenhall, 1994; Mia dan Clarke, 1999; Rasid dkk., 2017)

Hospital is an organization that provides health services, makes profits, and prioritizes the context of excellent services. Improving excellence in hospital services require actions, such as risk management. This enables the management to establish the potential risks arising from the activities in the hospital. Also, there is a need to manage the knowledge possessed by hospital employees for them to be more active in coordinating, planning, and evaluating, as well as improving excellent services (Darroch, 2005; Edvardsson dan Oskarsson, 2011; Gold dkk., 2001; Khalifa dan Shen, 2010). There should be a management accounting system that oversees all information related to company resources' potential to improve excellent services (Hammad dkk., 2010; Rasid dkk., 2014).

The hospital is a service that is quite similar to a psychological approach to both the patient and their family. The relationship between hospital employees, patients, and their families requires a distinctive psychological aspect in improving excellent services. The psychological aspect consists of spiritual intelligence and leadership, as well as individual spirituality. Individuals passionate about their job are mainly characterized by spirituality (Pawar, 2009; Petchsawang dan Duchon, 2012). Individuals with a high level of spirituality actively and continuously evaluate all their work to gain direction in producing better results (Chawla dan Guda, 2010; Marques, 2008; Yogatama dan Widayarni, 2015). They strive to offer their best to improve organizational performance through corrective actions in their activities (Indrajaya, 2017; Javanmard, 2012). The corrective action results from an awareness of individual responsibility to provide the best for the company, directed at improving its performance (Karakas, 2010; Pawar, 2009; Petchsawang dan Duchon, 2012).

This study examines the relationship between management accounting systems, risk management, knowledge management, CEO spirituality, and company performance. The study added knowledge management and CEO spirituality variables. Furthermore, the management accounting system was used as a mediating variable in the relationship between corporate risk management, knowledge management, and CEO spirituality with organizational company performance. Companies using a management accounting system obtain essential information that is timely and appropriate for managers. Therefore, they make better business decisions, which helps their company achieve advantages over their competitors. The use of management accounting systems as a mediating variable is in line with Ghasemi dkk. (2016). According to Ghasemi dkk. (2016), management accounting system significantly mediated the influence of competition on managerial performance. However, Rasid dkk. (2011) found that the management accounting system does not mediate the influence of innovation on organizational performance.

This study is explanatory research. The data were collected using questionnaires with a sample of 166 hospital directors in East Java Province, Indonesia. The structural equation modeling using WarpPLS was used in data analysis.

The results found that corporate risk management and knowledge management positively influenced the management accounting system and had no impact on company performance. The management accounting system mediates the influence of corporate risk and knowledge management on company performance in a complementary manner. Moreover, the management accounting system fully mediates the influence of CEO spirituality on company performance.

Hypothesis Development

Rasid dkk. (2014) provided empirical evidence that proper risk management improves management accounting systems. According to Rasid dkk. (2014) There exists a positive and significant relationship between perceived risk, risk management activities, and management accounting system indicators. Subsequently, higher risk management implementation increases the use of an external, future-oriented, and non-financial management accounting system. This creates a relationship and is summarized by periods, products, or various management fields.

H₁: Corporate risk management positively influences the management accounting system

Gornjak (2014) empirically showed that proper knowledge management produces a good management accounting system. According to Gornjak (2014), with changes in knowledge management, organizations are making adjustments resulting from the creation, dissemination, and use of new knowledge. The expansion of information technology has facilitated rapid development in the use of scientific knowledge.

The foundation of advancement in research and the transition from traditional to modern data accounting processes are strategic management processes. Using information technology, the organization creates new knowledge incorporated in its processes and spreads to management accounting among all its employees.

H₂: Knowledge management positively influences the management accounting system

Company management with a high spiritual awareness strives to effectively use management accounting systems to make the right decisions for the company based on the real problems (Dewsbury dan Cloke, 2009; Karakas, 2010; Malik dan Tariq, 2016).

H₃: Individual spirituality positively influences the management accounting system

Gnawali (2017) empirically showed that a good management accounting system improves company performance. According to Gnawali (2017), changes in the management accounting system significantly improve company performance. This means that changes in a management accounting system significantly improve bank performance based on their relationship as established in this study. The findings indicate that there is a significant impact on the management accounting system on company performance.

H₄: Management accounting system positively influences company performance

Florio dan Leoni (2017), Gordon dkk. (2009), Quon dkk. (2012) stated that corporate risk management positively influences company performance. Corporate risk management helps in absorbing information related to environmental changes, which is useful to the managers in making decisions for improving company performance.

H₅: Corporate risk management positively influences company performance

Ha dkk. (2016) empirically showed that good knowledge management improves company performance. The increasing importance of knowledge has motivated people to adopt knowledge management in developing their business strategy. Businesses must have a better understanding of the consequences of applying knowledge management

H₆: Knowledge management positively influences company performance

Petchsawang dan Duchon (2012), Malik dan Tariq (2016), Martin dan Hafer (2009), Dewsbury dan Cloke (2009) stated that working people commit themselves to their job, including their heart and soul. When people work with this kind of passion, performance is improved. A common phenomenon that is found in all human beings and includes their characteristics is spirituality. The ethical system produces one's experience with the job because it comes into a workplace with unique ethical values. Moreover, everyone has a different spiritual background in their initial internal nature (Karakas, 2010).

H₇: CEO spirituality positively influences company performance

The management accounting system encourages company managers to be more active in their performance. Company management becomes active in coordinating between divisions, evaluating, supervising, and investigating to obtain broader and more accurate information to minimize potential risks. It is motivated to improve managerial performance by creating a good handling process in dealing with potential risks, thereby improving company performance (Gnawali, 2017; Mia dan Clarke, 1999; Reid dan Smith, 2000; Soobaroyen dan Poorundersing, 2008).

H₈: The management accounting system positively mediates the influence of corporate risk management on company performance.

The management accounting system decides upon the knowledge that the company must have to improve business processes. An effective management accounting system in the company encourages managerial performance improvement and good decision-making (Soobaroyen dan Poorundersing, 2008). Company management becomes motivated to increase coordination and meet the needs and potential of each of its divisions. Furthermore, management strives to accumulate information through investigations, evaluation, and supervision, as well as decisions related to the company's needed knowledge. The management's efforts to improve coordination, investigation, evaluation and supervision produce useful knowledge for the company, helping improve performance.

H₉: The management accounting system positively mediates the influence of knowledge management on company performance

The ethical system in the company encourages individuals to increase their spiritual level in accomplishing their assigned work. Individual spirituality is the main characteristic for each person that is passionate in their job (Petchsawang dan Duchon, 2012). Individuals with a high spirituality level seek to evaluate all their work continuously, acting as a direction needed in their work. They strive to perform optimally by taking corrective actions in their work aimed at improving company performance. This corrective action results from an awareness of the individual responsibility to provide the best direction towards the improvement of company performance (Yogatama dan Widyarini, 2015).

H₁₀: The management accounting system positively mediates the influence of CEO spirituality on company performance

RESEARCH METHODS

This study is explanatory research. The primary data were collected using questionnaires. The study population consisted of the directors and deputy directors in each hospital with a classification of types A, B, and C in East Java. There was a total of 213 hospitals and a sample of 166 respondents. This study's independent variables were corporate risk management, knowledge management, management accounting system mediating variables, CEO spirituality, while the dependent variable was company performance. The variable indicators are found in appendix 1. The data were analyzed using the WarpPLS software version 5.0

RESEARCH RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive analysis provides an overview of the respondent's condition as additional information to understand the research results. It describes the gender, age, and employment period of the respondents used in this study.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

Respondent Characteristics By Gender			
Basic Classification	Sub-classification	Frequency	
		Absolute	Percentage
Gender	Male	119	72%
	Female	47	28%
Respondent Characteristics By Age			
Basic Classification	Sub-classification	Frequency	

		Absolute	Percentage
Age	1. 40 - < 45 Years	11	5.91%
	2. 45 - < 50 Years	47	25.27%
	3. 50 - < 55 Years	53	28.49%
	4. > 55 Years	75	40.32%

Respondent Characteristics By Length of Employment

Basic Classification	Sub-classification	Frequency	
		Absolute	Percentage
Length of employment	<5 Years	6	3,61%
	6-10 Years	36	21,69%
	11-15 Years	52	31,33%
	16-20 Years	54	32,53%
	>20 Years	18	10,84%

Source: Research data processed in 2019.

Results of the Study

This study used a Structural Equation Model (SEM) with Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis method to test the proposed hypothesis. PLS analysis was tested using WarpPLS software version 5.0 for windows to determine the influence of corporate risk management, knowledge management, management accounting systems, individual spirituality in workplaces, and company performance.

Based on the testing, all indicators have an outer loading factor value of more than 0.5. Therefore, all indicators are appropriate to reflect each of the related variables. All variables have discriminant validity values above 0.50. The reliability coefficient must be greater than 0.70. The results of the fit model test indicate that the model in this study is fit. SPR, RSCR, SSR, and NLBCDR have a value of more than 0.7. The results of the research model used in the calculation of hypothesis testing are shown in the following Figures 1 and 2 below:

Figure4.2. The figure of Final Literacy
Table2. Hypothesis Test Results
Direct Influence

The Relationship Between Variables	Path Coefficient	p-value
MRP -> KP	0,069	0,185

MRP ->SAM	0,144	0,029**
MP -> KP	0,096	0,105
MP ->SAM	0,156	0,020**
SI -> KP	0,001	0,496
SI ->SAM	0,114	0,067*
SAM -> KP	0,768	0,000***
Indirect Influence		
The Relationship Between Variables	Path Coefficient	p-value
MRP ->SAM -> KP	0,111	0,020**
MP ->SAM -> KP	0,120	0,013**
SI ->SAM -> KP	0,088	0,053***

Information: *, **, * significant at the level of 1%, 5%, 10%**

The results of statistical tests show that corporate risk management influences the management accounting system, meaning that H_1 is accepted with a p-value of 0,029 ($0,029 < 0,05$). Therefore, the increase in corporate risk management improves the management accounting system. The results showed that risk management is an effort by the hospital board of directors to collect and organize all information related to potential risks. The hospital board of directors uses this information to deal with the risks caused by environmental changes. Therefore, a management accounting system should be designed to organize data on each line of business and its competitors. The hospital board of directors uses this data as a company business decision (Laine dkk., 2012). The management accounting system assists the hospital board of directors in making a quick decision based on their potential. The convenience provided by the management accounting system encourages the hospital board of directors to strive and establish the correct data related to all its potential and make the right decision. (Rasid dkk., 2014).

The statistical test results show that knowledge management influences the management accounting system, meaning that H_2 is accepted with a p-value of 0,020 ($0,020 < 0,05$). Therefore, the increase in knowledge management improves the management accounting system. The results show that knowledge management directs company managers to accumulate and synergize the information from each department, which is useful in providing effective steps. A competent management accounting system must accompany the efforts of the company to improve knowledge management. With good knowledge management, the company minimizes contingency problems that may arise.

The statistical test results show that CEO spirituality influences the management accounting system, which means that H_3 is accepted with a p-value of 0,067 ($0,067 < 0,1$). Therefore, the increase in CEO spirituality improves management accounting systems. The results showed that the ethical awareness that shaped the hospital board of directors would form the spirituality that is necessary for solving the problems faced by the hospital based on the actual conditions. The spiritual awareness enables the board of directors enables to actively obtain the data related to emerging problems and effectively solve them.

The statistical test results show that the management accounting system influences company performance, indicating that H_4 is accepted with a p-value of 0,000 ($0,000 < 0,01$). Therefore, the increase in management accounting systems improves company performance. The results show that a management accounting system is a tool to absorb extensive information from internal and external parties. The management of this information is used to improve company performance.

The statistical test results show that corporate risk management does not influence company performance, meaning that H_5 is rejected with a p-value of 0,185 ($0,185 > 0,1$). Therefore, the increase in corporate risk management cannot improve company performance. The results showed that corporate risk management does not help company managers to identify the potential risks faced by the company. As a result, the potential risks become information that is processed by management to make a decision that is useful for improving company performance. These results are not in line with Florio dan Leoni (2017), Gordon dkk. (2009), Quondkk. (2012).

The statistical test results show that knowledge management does not influence company performance, meaning that H_6 is rejected with a p-value of 0,105 ($0,105 > 0,1$). Therefore, the increase in company knowledge management cannot improve company performance. The results of this study are not in line with Ha dkk. (2016), which empirically showed that good knowledge management improves company performance. The increasing importance of knowledge does not motivate business people to adopt knowledge management in developing their strategy.

The statistical test results show that CEO spirituality does not influence company performance, indicating that H_7 is rejected with a p-value of 0,496 ($0,496 > 0,1$). Therefore, the increase in CEO spirituality cannot improve company performance. The results showed that the spiritual awareness of the board of directors had not improved company performance. This is because, as a business entity, the hospital has to improve its performance. However, in the ethical sphere, the hospital is a social entity that must serve the public's needs related to health care regardless of its economic contribution. Therefore, hospital directors with good spiritual awareness have not improved hospital performance. These results are in line with Soha dkk. (2016), which empirically showed that CEO spirituality does not have a significant impact on improving company performance.

The statistical test results show that the management accounting system mediates corporate risk management's influence on company performance, which means that H_8 is accepted. Therefore, the increase in corporate risk management improves the management accounting system. In consequence, the increase in the management accounting system influences the improvement of company performance. The statistical test results show that the management accounting system mediates the influence of knowledge management on company performance, meaning that H_9 is accepted. Therefore, the management accounting system mediates the influence of knowledge management on company performance. The statistical test results show that the management accounting system does not mediate individual spirituality's influence on company performance, which means that H_{10} is rejected. Therefore, the management accounting system does not mediate the influence of individual spirituality on company performance.

Conclusions, Limitations, and Suggestions

Conclusion

The results showed that corporate risk management and knowledge management positively influenced the management accounting system, and had no influence on company performance. The management accounting system mediates the influence of corporate risk management and knowledge management on company performance in a complementary manner. Furthermore, the management accounting system fully mediates the influence of CEO spirituality on company performance.

Research Limitations and Directions for Future Researchers

This study has several limitations on the generalizations about existing phenomena. There are several limitations in the preparation of this research. First, the directors' busy activities at each hospital hampered the in-depth interviews related to the phenomenon. This raised the perception of each director that the phenomenon under study was only based on the distributed questionnaires. Second, the development of the research instrument used in data collection was a combination of at least 3 different studies in the same field, except for educational background indicators. This caused the lack of synchronization of the questions from the questionnaire, breeding complaints from the respondents.

Based on the limitations of this study, several suggestions are proposed. First, future studies should conduct direct interviews with each business unit manager to describe the phenomenon related to the variables used in this study. This will help obtain more comprehensive results, and provide a broader phenomenon regarding corporate risk management, knowledge management, CEO spirituality, management accounting systems, and company performance. Second, future studies should focus on the research instrument and the double-barrel problem that is likely to be faced.

REFERENCES

- Abdullatif, M., & Kawuq, S. (2015). The role of internal auditing in risk management: evidence from banks in Jordan. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 31(1), 30-50. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEAS-08-2013-0025>.
- Alaarj, S., Abidin-Mohamed, Z., & Bustamam, U. S. B. A. (2016). Mediating role of trust in the effects of knowledge management capabilities on organizational performance. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 235, 729-738. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.11.074>.
- Anshori, M., & Iswati, S. (2009). Buku Ajar Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif. *Surabaya: Pusat Penerbitan dan Percetakan UNAIR (AUP)*.
- Arjoon, S. (2000). Virtue theory as a dynamic theory of business. *Journal of business ethics*, 28(2), 159-178. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1006339112331>.
- Beckett, R. (2004). Communication ethics: Principle and practice. *Journal of Communication Management*, 8(1), 41-52. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13632540410807538>.
- Bento, R. F., Mertins, L., & White, L. F. (2018). Risk Management and Internal Control: A Study of Management Accounting Practice. *Advances in Management Accounting*, 1-25. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-787120180000030002>.
- Bertens, K. (2000). *Pengantar etika bisnis*: Kanisius.

- Berland, A. (2009). Virtue ethics in business and the capabilities approach. *Journal of business ethics*, 84(1), 25-32. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-008-9686-3>.
- Bogodistov, Y., & Wohlgemuth, V. (2017). Enterprise risk management: a capability-based perspective. *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 18(3), 234-251. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRF-10-2016-0131>.
- Busco, C., & Scapens, R. W. (2011). Management accounting systems and organizational culture: Interpreting their linkages and processes of change. *Qualitative Research in Accounting & Management*, 8(4), 320-357. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/1176609111189873>.
- Chawla, V., & Guda, S. (2010). Individual spirituality at work and its relationship with job satisfaction, propensity to leave and job commitment: An exploratory study among sales professionals. *Journal of Human Values*, 16(2), 157-167. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/097168581001600203>.
- Chenhall, R. H. (2003). Management control systems design within its organizational context: findings from contingency-based research and directions for the future. *Accounting, Organizations, and Society*, 28(2-3), 127-168. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-3682\(01\)00027-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-3682(01)00027-7).
- Chenhall, R. H., & Morris, D. (1986). The impact of structure, environment, and interdependence on the perceived usefulness of management accounting systems. *Accounting Review*, 16-35.
- Chia, Y. M. (1995). Decentralization, management accounting system (MAS) information characteristics and their interaction effects on managerial performance: a Singapore study. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 22(6), 811-830. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-5957.1995.tb00390.x>.
- Chin, W. W. (1998). *The Partial Least Squares Approach To Structural Equation Modeling* (Vol. 295).
- Chong, V. K., & Chong, K. M. (1997). Strategic choices, environmental uncertainty, and SBU performance: a note on the intervening role of management accounting systems. *Accounting and Business Research*, 27(4), 268-276. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00014788.1997.9729553>.
- Clifford, W., & Smith, J. (1995). Corporate risk management: theory and practice. *The journal of derivatives*, 30, 21, 31. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3905/jod.1995.407920>.
- Darroch, J. (2005). Knowledge management, innovation, and firm performance. *Journal of knowledge management*, 9(3), 101-115. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673270510602809>.
- Dewsbury, J.-D., & Cloke, P. (2009). Spiritual landscapes: existence, performance, and immanence. *Social & Cultural Geography*, 10(6), 695-711. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649360903068118>.
- Edvardsson, I. R., & Oskarsson, G. K. (2011). Knowledge management and value creation in service firms. *Measuring Business Excellence*, 15(4), 7-15. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13683041111184062>.
- Falk, R. F., & Miller, N. B. (1992). *A primer for soft modeling*: University of Akron Press.
- Florio, C., & Leoni, G. (2017). Enterprise risk management and firm performance: The Italian case. *The British Accounting Review*, 49(1), 56-74. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bar.2016.08.003>.
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of marketing research*, 18(1), 39-50. DOI: 10.2307/3151312.
- Fraser, J. R., & Simkins, B. J. (2016). The challenges of and solutions for implementing enterprise risk management. *Business horizons*, 59(6), 689-698. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2016.06.007>.
- Ghasemi, R., Azmi Mohamad, N., Karami, M., Hafiz Bajuri, N., & Asgharizade, E. (2016). The mediating effect of management accounting system on the relationship between competition and managerial performance. *International Journal of Accounting and Information Management*, 24(3), 272-295. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJAIM-05-2015-0030>.
- Gnawali, A. (2017). Management Accounting Systems and Organizational Performance of Nepalese Commercial Banks. *Journal of Nepalese Business Studies*, 10(1), 8-19. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3126/jnbs.v10i1.19129>.
- Gold, A. H., Malhotra, A., & Segars, A. H. (2001). Knowledge management: An organizational capabilities perspective. *Journal of management information systems*, 18(1), 185-214. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/07421222.2001.11045669>.
- Gordon, L. A., Loeb, M. P., & Tseng, C.-Y. (2009). Enterprise risk management and firm performance: A contingency perspective. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 28(4), 301-327. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccpubpol.2009.06.006>.
- Gordon, L. A., & Narayanan, V. K. (1984). Management accounting systems perceived environmental uncertainty and organization structure: an empirical investigation. *Accounting, Organizations, and Society*, 9(1), 33-47. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-3682\(84\)90028-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-3682(84)90028-X).
- Gornjak, M. (2014). *Knowledge Management and Management Accounting*. Paper presented at the International Conference DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.4907.4328.
- Ha, S.-T., Lo, M.-C., & Wang, Y.-C. (2016). Relationship between knowledge management and organizational performance: a test on SMEs in Malaysia. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 224, 184-189. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.05.438>.
- Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2011). PLS-SEM: Indeed, a silver bullet. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 19(2), 139-152. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2753/MTP1069-6679190202>.

- Hair, Jr, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2016). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*: Sage publications.
- Hair, Jr, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & G. Kuppelwieser, V. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) An emerging tool in business research. *European Business Review*, 26(2), 106-121. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-10-2013-0128>.
- Hair, Jr, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Gudergan, S. P. (2017). *Advanced issues in partial least squares structural equation modeling*: Sage Publications.
- Hammad, S. A., Jusoh, R., & Yen Nee Oon, E. (2010). Management accounting system for hospitals: a research framework. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 110(5), 762-784. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/02635571011044777>.
- Hansen, D. R., & Mowen, M. M. (2007). *Managerial accounting* 8th edition. USA: Thomson South-Western.
- Helfert, E. A. (1996). Teknik analisis keuangan: petunjuk praktis untuk mengelola dan mengukur kinerja perusahaan. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Indrajaya, A. N. (2017). The Influence of Individual Spirituality Toward Spirit at Work in Enhancing Organizational Commitment and Job Satisfaction. *International Journal of Business Studies*, 1(2), 51-59. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32924/ijbs.v1i2.19>.
- Javanmard, H. (2012). The impact of spirituality on work performance. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 5(1), 1961-1966.
- Kamtekar, R. (2004). Situationism and virtue ethics on the content of our character. *Ethics*, 114(3), 458-491. DOI: 10.1086/381696.
- Karakas, F. (2010). Spirituality and performance in organizations: A literature review. *Journal of business ethics*, 94(1), 89-106. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-009-0251-5>.
- Khalifa, M., & Shen, K. N. (2010). An integrated approach in developing knowledge management process capabilities.
- Khan, M. J., Hussain, D., & Mehmood, W. (2016). Why do firms adopt enterprise risk management (ERM)? Empirical evidence from France. *Management Decision*, 54(8), 1886-1907. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-09-2015-0400>.
- Koehn, D. (1995). A role for virtue ethics in the analysis of business practice. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 533-539. DOI: 10.2307/3857397.
- Laine, T., Paranko, J., & Suomala, P. (2012). Management accounting roles in supporting servitization: Implications for decision making at multiple levels. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 22(3), 212-232. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09604521211230969>.
- Lee, Y.-K., Kim, S.-H., Seo, M.-K., & Hight, S. K. (2015). Market orientation and business performance: Evidence from the franchising industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 44, 28-37. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09604521211230969>.
- Malik, M. S., & Tariq, S. (2016). Impact of spiritual intelligence on organizational performance. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 6(2), 289-297.
- Marques, J. F. (2008). Spiritual performance from an organizational perspective: the Starbucks way. *Corporate Governance: The international journal of business in society*, 8(3), 248-257. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/14720700810879141>.
- Martin, T. N., & Hafer, J. C. (2009). Models of emotional intelligence, spiritual intelligence, and performance: a test of Tischler, Biberman, and McKeage. *Journal of Management, spirituality, and religion*, 6(3), 247-257. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14766080903069364>.
- Mia, L., & Chenhall, R. H. (1994). The usefulness of management accounting systems, functional differentiation, and managerial effectiveness. *Accounting, Organizations, and Society*, 19(1), 1-13. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-3682\(94\)90010-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-3682(94)90010-8).
- Mia, L., & Clarke, B. (1999). Market competition, management accounting systems, and business unit performance. *Management Accounting Research*, 10(2), 137-158. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1006/mare.1998.0097>.
- Mills, A. M., & Smith, T. A. (2011). Knowledge management and organizational performance: a decomposed view. *Journal of knowledge management*, 15(1), 156-171. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673271111108756>.
- Ngah, R., Tai, T., & Bontis, N. (2016). Knowledge management capabilities and organizational performance in roads and transport authority of Dubai: The mediating role of the learning organization. *Knowledge and Process Management*, 23(3), 184-193. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/kpm.1504>.
- Nocco, B. W., & Stulz, R. M. (2006). Enterprise risk management: Theory and practice. *Journal of applied corporate finance*, 18(4), 8-20. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6622.2006.00106.x>.
- Nunnally, J. C., Bernstein, I. H., & Berge, J. M. t. (1967). *Psychometric theory* (Vol. 226): McGraw-Hill New York.

- Park, N., Peterson, C., & Seligman, M. E. (2004). Strengths of character and well-being. *Journal of social and Clinical Psychology, 23*(5), 603-619. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1521/jscp.23.5.603.50748>.
- Pawar, B. S. (2009). Individual spirituality, workplace spirituality, and work attitudes: An empirical test of direct and interaction effects. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal, 30*(8), 759-777. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437730911003911>.
- Petchsawang, P., & Duchon, D. (2012). Workplace spirituality, meditation, and work performance. *Journal of management, spirituality & religion, 9*(2), 189-208. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14766086.2012.688623>.
- Peterson, C., & Seligman, M. (2004). *Character Strengths and Virtues: A Classification and Handbook*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Quinn, J. J. (1997). Personal ethics and business ethics: The ethical attitudes of owners/managers of small businesses. *Journal of business ethics, 16*(2), 119-127. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1017901032728>.
- Quon, T. K., Zeghal, D., & Maingot, M. (2012). Enterprise risk management and firm performance. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences, 62*, 263-267. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.042>.
- Rasid, S. Z. A., Golshan, N., Mokhber, M., Tan, G.-G., & Mohd-Zamil, N. A. (2017). Enterprise risk management, performance measurement systems, and organizational performance in Malaysian Public Listed Firms. *International Journal of Business and Society, 18*(2), 311-328. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.33736/ijbs.543.2017>.
- Rasid, S. Z. A., Rahman, A. R. A., Ismail, W. K. W., Osman, M. H. M., & Amin, M. (2011). *The Mediating Effect of Management Accounting Systems on the Relationships between Contextual Variables and Organizational Performance*. Paper presented at the Global Business and Social Science Research Conference, Radisson Blu Hotel, Beijing, China.
- Rasid, S. Z. A., Ruhana Isa, C., & Khairuzzaman Wan Ismail, W. (2014). Management accounting systems, enterprise risk management, and organizational performance in financial institutions. *Asian Review of Accounting, 22*(2), 128-144. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/ARA-03-2013-0022>.
- Rayburn, J. M., & Rayburn, L. G. (1991). Contingency theory and the impact of new accounting technology in uncertain hospital environments. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal, 4*(2). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513579110005257>.
- Reid, G. C., & Smith, J. A. (2000). The impact of contingencies on management accounting system development. *Management Accounting Research, 11*(4), 427-450. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1006/mare.2000.0140>.
- Roof, R. A. (2015). The association of individual spirituality on employee engagement: The spirit at work. *Journal of business ethics, 130*(3), 585-599. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-014-2246-0>.
- Soha, H. M., Osman, A., Salahuddin, S. N., Abdullah, S., & Ramlee, N. F. (2016). The relationship of work influence, sense of community, and individual spirituality towards organizational performance. *Procedia Economics and Finance, 35*, 591-596. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(16\)00072-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(16)00072-1).
- Soin, K., & Collier, P. (2013). Risk and risk management in management accounting and control. In: Elsevier.
- Solomon, R. C. (1992). Corporate roles, personal virtues: An Aristotelean approach to business ethics. *Business Ethics Quarterly, 2*(3), 317-339. DOI: 10.2307/3857536.
- Solomon, R. C. (2003). Victims of circumstances? A defense of virtue ethics in business. *Business Ethics Quarterly, 13*(1), 43-62. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/3857858>.
- Soltanizadeh, S., Abdul Rasid, S. Z., Mottaghi Golshan, N., & Wan Ismail, W. K. (2016). A business strategy, enterprise risk management, and organizational performance. *Management Research Review, 39*(9), 1016-1033. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-05-2015-0107>.
- Soobaroyen, T., & Poorundersing, B. (2008). The effectiveness of management accounting systems: evidence from functional managers in a developing country. *Managerial Auditing Journal, 23*(2), 187-219. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/02686900810839866>.
- Subramaniam, N., Collier, P., Phang, M., & Burke, G. (2011). The effects of perceived business uncertainty, external consultants, and risk management on organizational outcomes. *Journal of Accounting & Organizational Change, 7*(2), 132-157. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/18325911111139671>.
- Sugiyono, P. (2008). Metode penelitian kuantitatif dan kualitatif dan R&D. *Bandung (ID): Alfabeta*.
- Tiwana, A. (2000). *The knowledge management toolkit: practical techniques for building a knowledge management system*: Prentice Hall PTR.
- Waldman, D. A., Ramirez, G. G., House, R. J., & Puranam, P. (2001). Does leadership matter? CEO leadership attributes and profitability under conditions of perceived environmental uncertainty. *Academy of management journal, 44*(1), 134-143. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5465/3069341>.
- Waterhouse, J. H., & Tiessen, P. (1978). A contingency framework for management accounting systems research. *Accounting, Organizations, and Society, 3*(1), 65-76. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-3682\(78\)90007-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-3682(78)90007-7).
- Wibisono, D. (2017). *Manajemen Kinerja Korporasi dan Organisasi*.

- Yogatama, L. A. M., & Widyarini, N. (2015). Kajian spiritualitas di tempat kerja pada konteks organisasi bisnis. *Jurnal Psikologi*, 42(1), 1-14. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22146/jpsi.6939>.
- Zack, M., McKeen, J., & Singh, S. (2009). Knowledge management and organizational performance: an exploratory analysis. *Journal of knowledge management*, 13(6), 392-409. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673270910997088>.

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